

Some environmental issues in space activities

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Abstract. The article deals with one of the problems of ecological safety of space activities. In particular, the legal regulation of space activities.

Key words: space, environment, safety.

Speaking about the legal regulation of space activities in the Republic of Kazakhstan, firstly it is necessary to note that in accordance with the Section 3 of Art. 4 of the Kazakhstan Republic Constitution, "universally recognized principles and international law norms and Kazakhstan Republic international treaties are an integral part of its legal system. If there are established other rules by Kazakhstan Republic international treaty than those stipulated by the law, then the international agreement rules will be taken into account".

Therefore, Kazakhstan guided by the international agreement provisions in the space activity field at their implementation of space activities, where Kazakhstan is participant of it.

However, giving a priority to international law, we cannot underestimate the importance and the role of national legal rules governing space activities of States – of Space Explorers.

At nowadays the legal regulation of space activities is a key element and plays an important role in ensuring the sustainable development of the national space industry in Kazakhstan Republic. At the same time, despite of large-scale programs implementation of the USSR research and outer space and celestial bodies' exploration the Soviet period of State astronautics is characterized by the absence of a legislative regulation of space activities.

Space Management in this period realized with the strict administration, decision-making and administration of the space activities rules by such authorities as the Ministers Council, Ministry of General Machine Building, the Ministry of Defense Industry and the Ministry of Defense. Unlike to other states implementing their space

use national programs (USA, France, Austria, and others.), a specialized government body in order to control the space industry in the USSR also not created.

In 1991 in connection with the collapse of the USSR the lack of legislative and legal regulation of the space sector operation puts the program of space exploration under compromised coagulation. In this regard, in the Republic of Kazakhstan become necessary to adopt legislation on space activities, as well as in the legal registration of the Kazakh space-management – in the creation of a specialized state executive authority for space activities.

In the USSR, in addition to the condition of legislation absence on space activities there had no legislative definition of the legal status of space infrastructure objects. Thus, since inception in 1955, the main objects of space infrastructure – "Baikonur" cosmodrome was to regime military installations. Its legal status is determined by secret normative - legal acts issued by the Ministry of Defence.

Norm analysis of the state legislation on space activities which is establishing the legal situation basis of space infrastructure objects allows us to conclude that there is currently no national base regulatory act in this area and nowadays the operating legal standards have a number of flaws.

The space legislation forming process in the Republic of Kazakhstan has led to the fact that it is currently made up of a significant number of legal documents at various levels, the greater part of it directly doesn't related to the space activities. In this regard, there emerged the need for the development and adoption "On Space Activities" Law in the Republic of Kazakhstan.

Lack of national legislation development on Space Activities becomes the reason that many of the rules of international space law are carry out only declarative. Indeed their effective implementation is possible only in cases of adoption by the State of specific provisions that develop regulations of international space law, establishing the legal responsibility of the state for their violation. This issue acquires particular relevance under modern conditions when the space resources use activities actively pursued not only by state space agencies and non-governmental organizations.

In parallel with the process of norm-formation under consideration in international law, there occurs emergence and development of national legal systems that regulate social relations arising in connection with the implementation of space activities.

At the same time the state of international space law has an impact on the development of national space legislation, wherein as well as positive and as negative – in the case of defects in the international legal instruments on specific issues.

References:

1. Abdullayev A. V. Space exploration and environmental problems. Chisinau, 1990.
2. The USSR for the peaceful use of outer space 1957-1985. Tom ,1-2. M., 1985.
3. Vasilenko V. A. "Responsibility of States for the offense. – Kyiv, 1976.
4. Vereshchetin B.C. International cooperation in space. Moscow, 1977.
5. Vinogradov ST. International legal regulation of the Environment (part of UN). Abstract of PhD thesis. , 1981.
6. Vinogradov ST. International law and the protection of the atmosphere. Moscow, 1987.
7. Gusev RK, V. Petrov Legal protection of nature in SSSR.M., 1979.